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Work Package 5

Exposome monitoring and metabolomics profiling

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the computational analyses, part of the concept of exposome monitoring using wearables devices, with systematic longitudinal sampling. That is, the bioinformatic pipelines developed for the HEAP project to comprehensively analyse the longitudinal exposome and metabolome of the recruited individuals. The wearables cohort in HEAP consists of healthy pregnant and non-pregnant women (N=100) followed up for at least four months with systematic longitudinal sampling using wearables devices and saliva and urine sampling (cohort described in detail in WP5 D5.1 deliverable entitled '*Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device*'). Our careful recruitment and monitoring of the cohort's individuals provide the basis for the wearable cohort, which enables the joint longitudinal assessment of the individual's external exposome, internal metabolome, and their interaction.

We have developed two specific pipelines to describe the different components of biotic exposure using wearables. First, Universal Fragment Classification (UFC) pipeline is a comprehensive exposome analysis pipeline for wearable metagenomes, which requires a minimum cell input and has already shown accurate and reproducible results. Second, specific species-level detection and phylogenetic variation analyses of the abundant microbes are ensured with our CSC-UPAS pipeline, which uses Metagenome Assembled Genomes (MAGs) and a large, curated reference database to quickly and accurately infer the phylogenetic variation of the abundant species detected. An important note here is that these pipelines are of superb sensitivity, demonstrated by the accurate detection of as little as 10 *E. coli* cells from the wearables sample.

Finally, the correlation of external and internal exposure (i.e., exposome) available from the wearables and saliva/urine samples metabolome, respectively, will enable a comprehensive view of the health status of the wearable cohort participants. Taken together, the comprehensive analyses of individuals' environmental abiotic and biotic exposure jointly with the internal metabolome will further deepen our understanding of the exposome and its role in human health.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
2	Introduction	5
3	Analysis pipelines	6
3.1	UFC exposome analysis pipeline	6
3.2	CSC-UPAS exposome pipeline	7
3.3	Correlation of individuals' exposome and metabolome	9
4	Summary and Future plans.....	11
5	References	12

2 Introduction

Exposome refers to all the exposures through one's lifetime¹, which has a significant impact on personal health. Our and others' published work suggests that we are exposed to a dazzling array of abiotic and biotic environmental contaminants in our daily lives, far beyond what was previously quantified and understood². We have already identified significant locational and seasonal patterns on both individuals' biological and chemical profiles, reflecting dynamic changes in samples collected from the same person using our comprehensive analysis pipeline and custom database. The patented UFC pipeline² can accurately detect as low as 10 *E. coli* cells and is highly reproducible. More importantly, we discovered that human exposomes differed substantially between individuals even located in the same general area (e.g., Bay Area), demonstrating that traditional monitoring data on broad areas can reflect only a fraction of the complexity and dynamics of an individual's environmental exposures. Moreover, understanding the species-level phylogenetic variation of microorganisms that humans are exposed to is important because pathogenic potential is often strain-specific. The CSC-UPAS pipeline^{5,6} can systematically assess the abundant microbial species composition and phylogenetic variation from the wearables-derived environmental exposome.

In one aspect, human health can be estimated from an individual's genome, microbiome, exposome and their complex interactions. Conventional methods typically focus on a single group of factors, so-called stressors, which fail to address the complex nature of the human exposome. Previously we have developed a network approach that combines the external exposome and internal environment to investigate how the external stressors impact the internal -omes and associate with human health³. Our method is the first to systematically link individuals' external environmental exposures with individuals' internal processes at the omics level. Using this comprehensive approach to systematically analyse the individual's exposome and metabolome will eventually provide unprecedented insights into the role of the exposome in human health.

3 Analysis pipelines

3.1 UFC exposome analysis pipeline

The Universal Fragment Classification (UFC) is an analysis pipeline patented for wearables metagenome analyses^{2,4}. The pipeline includes automatically splitting input sequence data for massively parallel database searching and associated output parsing. There is an integrated automatic evaluation of the input and output to see if the results are complete and a resume option in a case where prior searching steps are interrupted. Searching hundreds or thousands of metagenome contigs of nucleic acids through a massive database is a time-consuming and computationally extensive process, and therefore careful optimisations are needed to ensure a reasonable running time for each sample.

The UFC pipeline (Figure 1) starts with quality control of the data in which the sequencing reads will first go through duplication removal and then a quality check. The next step is to remove all human reads through human reference genome mapping. The de novo assembly using the megahit algorithm is used to assemble reads into contigs to increase the confidence of subsequent taxonomic classification. Finally, the high-quality contigs will be used to query against our custom-made database for taxonomic mapping using the Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA) method.

The UFC pipeline is a collection of scripts in shell and python, and the full pipeline will be available in CSC computing cloud for wearables metagenome analysis for HEAP. That is, as soon as the SD-Desktop (https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_desktop/) in CSC is fully integrated with the Hopsworks 3.0, the pipeline will be available for sensitive data analysis both in the CSC cloud and within the Hopsworks 3.0.

Figure 1. Overview of UFC pipeline

3.2 CSC-UPAS exposome pipeline

Previously, we have exploited our comprehensive metagenome assembly pipeline to systematically screen traces of microbial nucleic acids from environmental DNA, which has led, among others, to the detection of the oldest viral genome thus far ever sequenced⁶. The same pipeline is now curated for the comprehensive detection of bacterial, viral, fungi, archaea and protozoan species and their species-level phylogenetic variation, which is ideal to study the highly dynamic human biotic exposure and its association with human health and disease using wearables devices and deep sequencing of wearables metagenomes. The pipeline can use both metagenome and meta-transcriptome sequencing files, and it is available in the CSC supercomputing environment (www.csc.fi) under the Linux operating system. The pipeline involves the pre-processing of the raw sequence data (i.e., quality trim and deduplication), the removal of human-derived reads, if necessary, the build of contigs and metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) and phylogenetic inference of the compositionally abundant species taxa. Notably, the pipeline includes an extensive curation step for excluding false positive species taxa typical in complex metagenome data.

Figure 2. Flowchart of CSC-UPAS exposome pipeline.

An overview of the steps involved in the pipeline is shown in Figure 2. A concise summary of the workflow's most important steps is as follows:

- **Pre-processing:** Single or pair-end FASTQ -files are taken as input files. FASTQ-file is a file type provided by the massively parallel sequencing methods used for creating wearables metagenomes. FASTQ files are quality trimmed, including deduplication using Cutadapt, Trimmomatic, Picard and BBtools. Only high-quality reads are retained.
- If **human reads** need to be **removed**, a user can choose to filter them out through mapping against a reference human genome.
- Pre-processed single or paired-end high-quality metagenome and meta-transcriptome sequences are then used for **inferring contigs**, and further Metagenome Assembled Genomes (MAGs) with two different assembling algorithms: metaspades and megahit.
- **Quality control and normalisation:** Results of the de novo assembly is filtered for likely environmental contamination and quality scores of the dataset. Subsequently, the high-quality MAGs data is normalised and transformed for compositional analyses.
- Finally, the **phylogenetic inference** of the abundant species taxa and their compositional distribution is estimated using RaxML and R.

The CSC-UPAS pipeline is a collection of scripts in bash, python, Perl and R, and the full pipeline will be available in the CSC computing cloud for wearables metagenome analysis for HEAP. That is, as soon as the SD-Desktop (https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_desktop/) in CSC is

fully integrated with the Hopsworks 3.0, the CSC-UPAS pipeline will be available for sensitive data analysis also within the Hopsworks 3.0.

3.3 Correlation of individuals' exposome and metabolome

In our recently published paper³, we comprehensively and longitudinally characterised a multi-omics profile of a participant, including the exposome, metabolome, proteome, gut microbiome, cytokines, and blood tests. We found nearly 9,000 statistically significant correlations among nearly 1,700 exposures and health-related features. Specifically, positive correlations were more predominant than negative correlations between the exposome and the other -omes collected, and the biological exposome and metabolome were the most dispersive and correlated -omes. In addition, biological exposures and the metabolome had the most significant correlations within the exposome and internal multi-omics, respectively. Particularly, we found 4624 statistically significant correlations between the exposome and blood metabolome, with more positive correlations than negative. Most of the high degree correlated biological exposome components were fungi and were positively correlated with the cellular metabolites from blood (Figure 3). Salicylic acid, dinoseb and dibromoethane were the top three environmental chemicals that correlated mostly positively with the cellular metabolites from blood. Pathway analysis revealed that most correlated pathways were associated with liver and kidney functions (Figure 4). Some pathways were correlated with both biological and chemical exposomes, such as protein digestion and absorption and aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis, whereas some pathways were only correlated with the biological exposome. This seminal work was the first to study the correlations between the external exposome and the internal multi-omics of the same individual. The study demonstrated the power of using a systematic approach to monitoring the individual's personal environmental health using wearables devices and inter-omics analyses.

Briefly, Spearman's correlation was used to build the correlations between the exposome and metabolome. Significant metabolites were kept to construct the correlation network and further investigate the associated pathways. KEGGs database was used for pathway enrichment analysis. Metabolic features connecting the exposome and metabolome were used to identify dysregulated modules based on metabolic networks from KEGGs database using maximum likelihood estimation.

With our comprehensive exposome approach, we here demonstrate that it is possible to identify high-degree components that are essential among the

Figure 4. Significant correlated metabolic pathways using the KEGG database.

4 Summary and Future plans

We have successfully built two pipelines to comprehensively analyze the external exposome from wearables metagenomes with the internal metabolome of the host and a third pipeline to estimate their likely interactions. The correlation of external and internal exposomes in high resolution will bring a comprehensive view of the health status of the cohort participants and, more importantly, give new insights into the diversity of human exposomes.

So far, the pipelines have been tested with UPAS wearables metagenome samples. In the last HEAP BYOD held in Stockholm (22-25 November 2022) we tested metagenome samples from few wearables. Metabolome data and correlation analyses described in this deliverable was produced by Snyder's lab.

HEAP will demonstrate a proof-of-concept for longitudinal exposome monitoring and pipeline analyses to understand the potential health effects of the external exposome during pregnancy.

All the pipelines described here will be available in the CSC computing cloud for wearables metagenome analysis for HEAP. Moreover, as soon as the SD-Desktop (https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_desktop/) in CSC is fully integrated with HEAP Hopsworks 3.0 the pipelines will be available for sensitive data analysis also within the HEAP Hopsworks 3.0. Once the pipelines are exhaustively tested and published, the source code will be available through the HEAP GitHub repository.

The WP5 pipelines will be aligned with the work from WP8 and WP9 (Epigenomics and metagenomics analyses) to enrich the analyses pipelines by providing integrated analyses for exposome research.

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